

FUTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE INFORMATION CULTURE OF A TEACHER IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

Mardanova Firuza Subkhonovna

Senior teacher at Samarkand state architecture and civil engineering university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8150787>

Abstract. *The article presents the findings of scientific investigation into the issue of future teacher preparation under the influence of information technology. The author emphasizes the importance of informatization of education, the preparation of foreign language teachers who will teach in the future, and the development of their information competency in professional activity using a method of the study of theoretical sources.*

Keywords: *information competence, information technologies, informatization, professional activity, educational activity, pedagogical activity.*

Information culture is a concept that is often found in specialized pedagogical literature. Most often it is used in relation to students. For them, information culture or media culture implies fundamental (basic) knowledge and skills in the field of information search and semantic processing, which ensure effective information activity. Without this knowledge and skills, successful educational and professional activity is fundamentally impossible, it is the key to information security.

The information culture of a teacher is more often seen as a willingness and ability to use ICT in the classroom. However, this concept should be considered much broader. On the one hand, given that the main function of a teacher is training and education, the ability to select, structure and adapt information is important in the context of a constant increase in the volume of information [1]. In addition, the specificity of pedagogical activity involves speaking at teachers' councils, summarizing experience, writing articles, etc., which also requires some preparation in terms of the ability to work with information, transform it and present it.

For the first time the concept of "information literacy" was introduced in the United States in 1977, while an information literate person was called a person who is able to identify, place, evaluate information and use it most effectively. Today, in connection with the development, first of all, of computer technologies, the transition to the stage of information development of society, we can say that information literacy has become the basis for information culture, which, as a concept, has many formulations [2]. All definitions can be divided into two large groups: in relation to society as a whole and in relation to the individual. In the first case, information culture is considered as:

- a separate area of culture, which is associated with the functioning of information in society and the formation of informational qualities of a particular person;
- a specific level of formation of information processes, the level of creation, collection, processing and storage of information, the degree of satisfaction to a certain extent of human needs in information communication;

- the ability of society to effectively use information resources and means of information communications, as well as to apply for these purposes advanced achievements in the development of informatization and information technologies.

Some experts believe that information culture perfectly characterizes the levels of development of a particular society, a particular nation or nationality, as well as specific areas of activity such as, for example, culture, art, life or work [3].

In relation to an individual, the term "information culture" is interpreted as:

- the totality of knowledge that a person possesses, the ability to use it in practice to solve certain problems;
- a qualitative indicator of the vital activity of a particular person in the field of receiving, transmitting, storing and applying information, where the main ones are spiritual universal values;
- a certain level of knowledge that enables a person to freely navigate in the information space without obstacles, take an active part in its formation and promote information interaction by all means.

Doctor of Psychology L.A.Kandybovich singles out the information culture of an organization, which determines the quality of information exchange in it and includes a number of components: information competence, high sensitivity to the object of its activity, communication culture [4].

Experts note that information culture at the level of society manifested itself in five information revolutions:

- discovery of the language;
- find of writing;
- basis of printing;
- the invention of electricity;
- application of computer technologies.

Modern information culture combines all of its previous forms. It acts as an object, result and means of social activity, well reflects the nature and level of human practical activity. Signs that a person has mastered the information culture are the following:

- the ability to adequately express their need for certain information;
- the ability to process the received information and create a new one;
- effectively search for the necessary data;
- the ability to adequately evaluate information;
- the ability to correctly select the necessary data;
- ability to computer literacy and information communication.

Information culture is not limited to disparate knowledge and skills of working with a computer or other technical means. It implies an informative orientation of a holistic personality, which is motivated to apply and assimilate new knowledge.

REFERENCES

1. Library of abstracts and dissertations on pedagogy: <http://nauka-pedagogika.com/pedagogika-13-00-01/dissertaciya-informatsionnaya-kultura-sovremennogo-pedagoga-kak-faktor-ego-professionalnogo-razvitiya>
2. Sokolova O.I. Information culture of teachers as a necessary component of modern education (http://rspu.edu.ru/university/publish/pednauka/1_2003/08sokolova.htm)

3. Pedagogy: Textbook for students of pedagogical educational institutions / V.A. Slastyonin, I.F. Isaev, A.I. Mishchenko, E.N. Shiyanov. - M .: School-Press, 1998
4. Electronic library of dissertations: <http://www.dissercat.com/content/informatsionnaya-kultura-kak-komponent-imidzha-sovremennogo-pedagoga>
5. Kornilov. M.V. Formation of information culture of the teacher in the system of advanced training (<http://lib.urfu.ru>)